

Documenting Military Occupation on Archaeological Sites

FROM THE IMPACTS ON ANCIENT REMAINS TO MODERN CONFLICT ARCHAEOLOGY

Mathilde MURA¹

Résumé : Documenter l'occupation militaire sur les sites archéologiques

Cet article interroge la position stratégique des tells archéologiques dans le paysage et leur utilisation comme bases militaires. Que ce soit en Irak ou en Afghanistan, les tells archéologiques dominent les plaines et sont souvent réemployés comme des points de contrôle surélevés et facilement défendables par les forces armées. L'étude considère comme bases militaires des installations souvent peu impressionnantes mais néanmoins invasives, telles que des levées de terre ou des baraquements. Deux axes de réflexion seront examinés ici. D'une part, nous mesurerons l'impact de ces installations sur les sites archéologiques (morphologie générale des tells, impact sur les vestiges et la stratigraphie) à l'aide des résultats carto-interprétés et des résultats issus des travaux de prospections. Puis nous considérerons le potentiel de ces résultats pour l'archéologie des conflits modernes. Pour cela, nous examinerons la répartition des sites, les points de contrôle et de défense naturels et les connaissances acquises sur les bases militaires de ces régions. Cette double perspective permettra ainsi d'appréhender les sites archéologiques dans leurs contextes modernes et anciens. Notre démarche tend vers une communication des données entre les protagonistes collectant les informations pour la protection des sites archéologiques et les acteurs de l'archéologie des conflits contemporains.

Mots-clés : tells archéologiques, occupation militaire, dégâts, impacts, conflits, méthodologie.

Abstract : This paper addresses the question of the strategic position of archaeological tells in the landscape and their use as military bases. Whether in Iraq or in Afghanistan, archaeological tells dominate the plains and are often occupied as high ground control points by the armed forces. In most cases, what the study considers as a base, only consists of small yet invasive installations, such as earth levees or barracks. Two focus points will be considered in this paper. On the one hand, I will measure the impact of these installations on ancient remains (general morphology of the tells, ruins and stratigraphy) by both cartography and survey results. On the other hand, I will interrogate the potential of those results towards an archaeology of modern conflict. In this second matter, I will consider a distribution analysis of the sites, natural access points and acquired knowledge on the military bases. This double perspective will help building a general comprehension of the sites. This approach aims at bridging the gap between monitoring site damage and exploiting the data thus collected towards modern conflict archaeology.

Key words : archaeological tells, military occupation, damages, impacts, conflicts, methodology.

¹. PhD Candidate, Université Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne, UMR 7041 ArScAn, VEPMO.

Unless specified otherwise figures are made by the author.

توثيق الإشغال العسكري على المواقع الأثرية: من الأثر على الآثار القديمة إلى علم آثار الصراع الحديث

يبحث هذا المقال في الموقع الاستراتيجي للتلال الأثرية للمشهد الطبيعي واستخدامها كقواعد عسكرية. سواء أكان في العراق أو في أفغانستان، تنتشر البقايا الأثرية في السهول وغالباً ما يتم استخدامها كنقاط مرتفعة للمراقبة، كما يمكن عبرها الدفاع بسهولة بواسطة القوات المسلحة. تعتبر هذه الدراسة أن منشآت القواعد العسكرية غالباً ما تكون غير مؤثرة ولكنها بدورها تحتاح الموقع، مثل أعمال الحفر أو تأسيس الشكات. سيتم هنا نقاش محورين من الموضوع. سنقوم بقياس تأثير هذه المنشآت على المواقع الأثرية (التشكيل العام للتلال، التأثير على البقايا والطبقات) بمساعدة النتائج المفسرة من الخرائط ونتائج أعمال فحص الموقع. ثم سننظر في إمكانات هذه النتائج لاستخدامها في علم آثار الصراعات الحديثة. وللقيام بذلك، سنبحث في توزع المواقع ونقاط المراقبة والدفاع الطبيعية والمعرفة المكتسبة عن القواعد العسكرية لهذه المناطق. سيساعد هذا المنظور المزودج على فهم المواقع الأثرية في سياقها الحديثة والقديمة. يتجه المنهج الذي نتبعه نحو نقل المعلومات بين الأطراف الفاعلة التي تجمع المعلومات لحماية المواقع الأثرية والجهات الفاعلة في علم آثار الصراعات المعاصرة.

الكلمات المفتاحية: المواقع الأثرية، الإشغال العسكري، الضرر، الآثار، النزاعات، المنهجية.

به دوکۆمیتکردنی نیشته جیبوونی سه‌بازی له شوینه شوینه‌واریه‌کان: له سه‌ر کاریگه‌ری له سه‌ر پاشماوه کۆنه‌کاندا بۆ ناکۆکی نۆی شوینه‌واری. ئەم توێژینه‌وه‌یه له شوینی ستراتیژی گرده شوینه‌واریه‌کان ده‌کرێته‌وه له ده‌شتایه‌کان و به‌کارهێنانیان وه‌ک بنکه‌ی سه‌ربازی. چ له عێراق یا له ئه‌فغانستان بێت، گرده شوینه‌واریه‌کان ده‌روانه سه‌ر ده‌شته‌کان و وه‌ زۆرجار به‌کارهاتوه‌ وه‌ک خالی پشکنین و چاودێری له لایه‌ن هێزی چه‌کداره‌وه. توێژینه‌وه‌ی بنکه سه‌ربازیه‌کان زۆر جیگای سه‌رنج نه‌بووه به‌لگه‌ شوینی داگیر کراو بووه وه‌ بۆ به‌ر به‌سه‌ر و چالێ به‌رگری سه‌ربازی. دوو ئاراسته‌ی بێرکده‌وه لێره‌دا شیده‌کرێته‌وه، له روونیکان، هه‌له‌سه‌ستین به‌ پێوانه‌کردنی کاریگه‌ری بنکه سه‌ربازیه‌کان له سه‌ر ناوچه شوینه‌واریه‌کان (شیوه‌ی گشتی گرده‌که، کاریگه‌ری له سه‌ر پاشماوه و چینه‌کان) به‌ هاوکاری ئه‌نجامه‌کان که‌وا به‌ پێی خواست و ئه‌نجامی هه‌له‌کۆلین رازه‌ی بۆ ده‌کرێت. ئه‌نجا ده‌روانینه‌ توانای ئه‌وه ئه‌نجامه‌یه‌ی زانستی شوینه‌وار له ناکۆکیه نوێیه‌کان، بۆ ئه‌نجامدانی ئه‌مه، هه‌له‌سه‌ستین به‌ لیکۆلینه‌وه له دابه‌ش بوونی ناوچه‌کان و خاله‌کانی چاودێری سرروشتی و به‌رگری و زانیاری ده‌سته‌وتوو له بنکه سه‌ربازیه‌کان ئه‌وه ناوچه‌یه. ئەم تێروانینه‌ یارمه‌تیان ده‌دا بۆ تێگه‌یشتن له ناوچه شوینه‌واریه‌کان له چوارچێوه‌ی نۆی و کۆن. ئەم رێچکه‌یه‌مان گرت بۆ گواسته‌وه‌ی زانیاریکان بۆ به‌دوورخستنه‌وه‌ی هه‌موو زانیاریه‌کان بۆ پاراستنی ناوچه شوینه‌واریه‌کان و لایه‌ن کاریگه‌ریه‌کانی سه‌ر زانستی شوینه‌وار له ناکۆکیه‌ هاوچه‌رخیه‌کاندا.

ووشه‌ی تێپه‌ر: گرده شوینه‌واریه‌کان، نیشته‌گه‌ی سه‌ربازی، زیانه‌کان، کاریگه‌ریه‌کان، ناکۆکیه‌کان، میتۆدۆلۆجی (مه‌نه‌جی یا رێباز)

اسناد سازی مکان‌های نظامی در ساحات باستانی: از تأثیرات آن در بقایای قدیم تا باستان شناسی درگیری‌های مدرن
این مقاله موقعیت استراتژیک تپه‌های باستانی را در چشم انداز و استفاده آنها را منحصراً پایگاه‌های نظامی مورد مطالعه قرار میدهد. تپه‌های باستانی چه در عراق و افغانستان در فراز جلگه‌ها استوار بوده و معمولاً منحصراً نقاط بلند قابل کنترل و به راحتی قابل تصرف برای قوای نظامی است. تپه‌های مورد مطالعه به تأسیساتی نه‌ آنقدر برجسته اما تهاجمی، مانند بلندی‌های زمین یا پایگاه‌ها اطلاق میشوند. درین مقاله، دو موضوع مورد بررسی قرار خواهند گرفت. از یک جهت، ما تأثیرات این چنین ساخته‌ها را روی ساحات باستانی (ریخت شناسی عمومی تپه‌ها، تأثیرات روی بقایای باستانی ولایه‌ها)، که در نتیجه‌ی تفسیر-نقشه‌ها و یا هم سروی ساحات بدست می‌آید، را اندازه‌گیری نموده و متعاقباً پتانسیل این نتایج را برای باستان شناسی درگیری‌های مدرن مد نظر می‌گیریم. بدین منظور ما پراکندگی ساحات، نقاط طبیعی دفاع و کنترل و شناخت از پایگاه‌های نظامی این مناطق را مورد بررسی قرار می‌دهیم. این ژرفانمایی دوباره، امکان این را برای ما فراهم می‌سازد، که ساحات باستانی را در وضعیت قدیمی و مدرن آنها درک نمایم. اقدامات ما بعداً منجر به تبادل اطلاعات بین پیشگامان که این معلومات را برای حفاظت از ساحات باستانی گرد آوری میکنند و کسانی که باستان شناسی درگیری‌های مدرن را مطالعه میکنند، میگردد.
واژه‌های کلیدی: تپه‌های باستانی، اشغال نظامی، خسارات، تأثیرات، درگیری‌ها، متدولوژی (روش شناسی).

logical survey data, the Balkh Oasis is an archaeological centre comprising over 2000 archaeological sites⁷. As part of the aforementioned project, 335 tells inside the area were monitored, partially surveyed by the author and remotely sensed. This area henceforth referred to as BDS (Balkh Damage Survey), currently includes 60 military occupied sites.

Regarding the historical context of the conflicts, we are looking at two very different situations. In the Shahrizor Plain, all damages date back to the Iran-Iraq War (1980-1988), more precisely to the end of the conflict when the 43rd Iraqi division fought against the 55th Iranian parachutist division and the 84th Iranian division for the city of Halabja⁸. Right after the Iraqi defeat in March 1988, Saddam Hussein intensified the Anfal operation and ordered chemical attacks against Halabja⁹. Besides these events, it is also necessary to mention the massive mining campaign led by Saddam Hussein Regime against agricultural and farming activities¹⁰. On this last point, fieldwork must take security measures due to the uncertainty of the mine clearing¹¹. The Plain was successively conquered and simultaneously occupied by the Iranian Army, the Iraqi Army and Kurdish troops trying to maintain their borders and to control the dams. Dams are indeed the main reason for the Iranian interest in the region: by controlling the dams, they wish to diminish the electric production and consequently the oil production and exportation of Iraq¹². With this in mind, military occupations in the Shahrizor Plain are naturally roughly contemporary to each other but the issue would be to attribute it to either of the belligerents.

In Afghanistan, the Balkh Oasis has been the theatre of many events over years of conflicts. In this area, the main issue lies

in attributing the damages to a certain period of time. During the Soviet invasion of Afghanistan (1978-1989), Mazar-i Charif¹³ and the Oasis were far enough from the heart of the battlefield. In the beginning of the period of the Islamic State of Afghanistan, the region succeeded in maintaining this relative peace.

After 1994, however, fights over Mazar-i Charif escalated, with mainly sectarian violence and three major massacres perpetrated between 1997 and 1998¹⁴. In 1998, the Taliban took control of Mazar-i Charif, and within the following years of most of the northern territories of Afghanistan¹⁵. Yet, in 2001, the simultaneous *Northern Alliance* and US Army offensives inflicted the first defeat in the area on the Taliban and opened land and air supply routes¹⁶. The Taliban withdrew to the north and west ends of the Oasis, where they are still controlling a large territory. In the meantime, American forces and the *Northern Alliance* had been controlling Mazar-i Charif and Balkh, and a small perimeter around each city. After 2002, both cities came back under the control of the central administration, firstly with the Karzai administration and the deployment of the 209th Corps of the Afghan National Army¹⁷. They locally established their military barracks on high grounds – most of them being archaeological sites.

In this context, it is the fact that Taliban bases have scattered over the landscape for over thirty years that might be an issue in analysing the damages. Furthermore, their installations have hardly changed in shape or mode of construction over the years, making the attribution to a specific period of time even more difficult.

8. RAZOUX 2013, p. 450-452.

9. Even though the operation began in 1987, it is the episode of Halabja that raised the most awareness in the international community (RAZOUX 2013, p. 451, JAMES & GORGAS 2018, p. 196).

10. Over 15 million landmines in Kurdish territory according to JAMES & GORGAS 2018, p. 196-197.

11. With the advice of both S. Mühl and the Direction of Antiquities in Sulaymaniyah, HDS respected the same safety measures as within the SSP (MUELH & FASSBINDER 2016) asking local person in the villages nearest to each site for information and renouncing to survey some sites when doubts remained.

12. RAZOUX 2013, p. 450-452.

13. The regional capital of Balkh Province.

14. THE AFGHANISTAN JUSTICE PROJECT 2005, p. 90, p. 115, p. 120.

15. THE AFGHANISTAN JUSTICE PROJECT 2005, p. 64.

16. GUARDIAN STAFF 2001.

17. RADIN 2009.

1. COLLECTION OF DATA, TYPOLOGY OF DAMAGES

Prior to field investigation, the two areas of study were remotely sensed in order to select a sample of sites and to identify the damages. Pre-zoning was also undergone in order to facilitate the survey. In the field, damaged archaeological sites were surveyed, and data collected from damages on every site. All military structures have been documented due to their uniqueness (we rarely observe rows of identical buildings, trench or earth levee on a site). The documentation consists in GPS localisation, measurements, description, sketches and photographs. Those measurements are especially informative as regards the depth and height of the damages. It enables us to better identify the signals for non-surveyed sites when doing remote sensing¹⁸. Moreover, ammunitions and shells present on site were carefully documented (only scaled photography in situ to avoid contact). Then, all the field data was transposed into the GIS and linked to external data for analysis.

Based on this fieldwork, it is possible to define a typology of military damages affecting archaeological sites and to begin to analyse their impact on the stratigraphic remains. There are four main elements that signal a military facility : barracks (2.a) ; trenching and levees (2.b) ; occasionally tank caches at the bottom of the slope or firing positions along the trenches (2.c) ; impact holes from air-to-ground and ground-to-ground strikes (2.d).

1.1. Military barracks

First of all, the barracks are distinguished by their construction materials. In the corpus under study, I have noticed barracks built either from cement blocks or from mud bricks. Other few examples were constructed of HESCO bags, a type well documented in Babylon, for instance¹⁹. For the block category, only three formats have been identified (small, medium and large units) in HalabjaDS (HDS) and another larger one in BalkhDS (BDS). Regarding the mud brick structures, a great variability of shapes and construction methods is noticeable, making each category unique in its kind. The most concerning type would be the semi-underground architecture – cutting through stratigraphy – which is quite frequent. In terms of shape, this type can be a simple quadrangular barracks, a T or L shaped building, or dome barracks.

a. Corona Imagery, 1969

b. Bing Imagery 2015

FIG. 3: Satellite views of Bngird Muani (HDS.44 or SSP.12) a. CORONA imagery, 1969 b. Bing Imagery, 2015.

Military occupation is generally characterised by major ground modifications consisting of levelling, implantation of trenches or earth levees. Levelling is the most impacting of these modifications and is required when implementing barracks on top of the sites. On the site of Bngird Muani (HDS.44 or SSP.12), for instance, a large tell located to the northwest of the Shahrizor Plain, the flattening of the top of the tell is now doubtlessly identified. Even though we do not always find the spoiled earth, interviews with locals can attest to the event, as well as comparison between pre-war imagery (such as CORO-

18. For this reason, the second phase of remote sensing was implemented after all field surveys were conducted.

19. INTERNATIONAL COORDINATION COMMITTEE FOR THE SAFEGUARDING OF THE CULTURAL HERITAGE OF IRAQ, SUB-COMMITTEE ON BABYLON 2009.

NA imagery commonly used in archaeology²⁰) and modern satellite captures (GeoEye or WorldView). Such imagery constitutes a more substantial evidence of the condition of the site in the past (Figure 3.a). On the 1969 picture, the presence of two prominences on the southeast and northwest edges of the site are potential signatures for eroded buildings, such as ancient towers that would have been destroyed by the levelling (Figure 3.b).

FIG. 4: Sketches of concrete block military barracks for HDS.

Military barracks themselves sometimes have only a minimal impact on the stratigraphy. Yet, it is still worth documenting it today for future archaeological excavations, especially when such structures are made of the same material as archaeological remains. In Afghanistan, for instance, a variety of military barracks were recorded²¹, most of them made of mud bricks and some made of military HESCO bags filled with sand. Conversely, only one type of barracks has so far been recorded in Iraqi Kurdistan, varying in size and made of cement blocks. The cemented type (Figure 4) is the less intrusive one, as the barracks can be built without foundations. It is the only type found in the Shahrizor Plain area. On more than half of the sites studied, we are looking at small units, composed of an entrance corridor and two perpendicular rooms (three rooms on the larger units).

For the cemented types, only the compaction effect can damage the stratigraphy, when no levelling was required for the implementation.

Afghan barracks, on the contrary, raise more issues. First of all, they are made of mud bricks. Once the building material is degraded, it can be mistakenly interpreted as remains of ancient structures made of the same material if there are no modern finds associated with the buildings. Secondly, Afghan barracks are often partially built underground, requiring digging onto the top layers of the site. The last type found in Afghanistan, impressive by its size of 25 m by 25 m, is very similar to the Iraqi concrete block barracks, but it is surrounded by a sand bag fence. Still, we have an issue regarding the entrance point, which might have been possible by a ladder or an underground access (the second option being more intrusive to the site).

1.2. Trenches and levees

Levelling can also be associated with the implementation of earth levees, most likely made of the removed sediment from the centre. Such levees are rudimentary and made with the most accessible material. The elevation of this pile of sediment can be between half a metre and two-and-a-half metres after twenty-five years of erosion. Both type of features are usually implemented with one or two entry points. Some exceptions could be noticed with special features such as a double earth levee marking the access, as for HDS.13 (Figure 5).

They usually serve as defensive features surrounding the top of the site. A combination of both trenches and levees was found in our corpus and is also observed in Syria, with the most compelling example of Ebla²². In our corpus, three depth levels have been noted for trenches (shallow : $H \leq 0.50$ m ; medium depth : $0.50 \text{ m} \leq H \leq 1$ m ; deep : $H \geq 1$ m), and are detectable by satellite imagery given the fact that field measurements were taken.

In few sites, lower trenches have also been recorded at the bottom of the slopes. They could belong to a system combining top trenches or earth levees, and are considered as a second defensive features. Ground measurements enabled the extrapolation of the depth intervals in the reading of satellite imagery : shallow trenches are usually larger and are visible by a slight contrast between the surrounding soil and the bottom sediment ; most common trenches are between 0.5 and

20. PHILIP *et al.* 2002; CASANA & COTHREN 2015.

21. This diversity may be explain by the succession of different conflicts. So far, no pattern was found nor specific shapes related to a conflict in particular.

22. KAERCHER *et al.* 2018.

FIG. 5: Satellite view of Grdy Hama Amin (HDS.13) showing the double levee access ramp, BingImagery 2015.

1 m deep. Their profile is eroded and the contrast between surrounding sediments and the bottom of the trench is more pronounced. A few sites yield evidence for trenches deeper than 1 m : 1.3 m at Alaman Tepe (BDS.13) and 1.2 m at Gird-i Qulk Hurd (HDS.21 or SSP.19). When not covered by vegetation, the trenches display steeper and straighter edges that increase the colour contrast between the top and the bottom soil viewed from the sky. This difference in colours and shades can also be explained by the perforation of stratigraphic layers.

1.3. Firing positions and tank caches

Some trenches are flanked with firing positions consisting of small notches on their outer edge. Generally quadrangular, as in Topa Rostam (BDS.1), they are sometimes rounded, as is the case in Bakr Awa (HDS. 34 or SSP.10). The shooting positions can either be found on a section or on the entire periphery of the trench, such as BDS.1 (Figure 6).

Finally, tank caches also consist of notches, grouped (often by three or four) and organised in a parallel disposition. They are usually not exposed to the frontline and entrenched on the slope behind the tell.

FIG. 6: Ground photography of Topa Rostam (BDS.1) showing the surrounding trench and detail of a firing position.

The size of the notches can be easily matched with the different kinds of vehicles used by the military. Directly linked to the presence of these tank caches, traffic also causes significant damage to the sites. Access roads protected by trenches and levees are often distinguished at the bottom of the sites, which also attest to the presence of heavy vehicles on sites (tanks, oil or food transport trucks). The repeated passage of these machines causes smooth or chained tracks that can be more or less deep depending on the condition of the ground (wet soils, for example, induce a deeper furrow), therefore producing both surface stigmas and compaction phenomena of the underlying stratigraphy. This phenomenon of stratigraphic compression is the same as the one commonly observed when excavating under roads or wheelbarrow paths, even on sites with no military occupation.

1.4. Air-to-ground and ground-to-ground impacts

The impact of ground-to-ground or air-to-ground strikes is the fourth and last type of effects of military activity on archaeological sites. In the current corpus, very few signatures can be related to this kind of impact, but some exploded and unexploded ordnances have been found, as well as warning signs for mined areas.

These impacts are characterised by a circular shape with diameters that vary in the ratio of one to three depending on the type of projectile. The shape and size of the impact craters also varies in depth. The contact zone of the explosion is characterised by a light area at the bottom of the depression surrounded by a second part that is still recessed but darker. On the surface, the dispersion of sediments causes a clear and homogeneous halo around the impact. By analogy with volcanic phenomena, the surrounding sediments should form a heterogeneous strip in granulometry in cross section. The angle of the impact may slightly alter the circular shape and cause a deformation of the halo. The lateral distribution of the ejected sediments and halo noticed in plan makes it possible to distinguish between a vertical "air-to-ground" and a "ground-to-ground" impact induced by a mine²³.

2. MODERN CONFLICT ARCHAEOLOGY

From this dataset, I chose case studies that can relay to modern conflict research questions.

Further on, the method consists of an experimental part in order to test my documentation for other areas and fields of research. In the Shahrizor and Balkh landscapes, I wish to start shedding light on some intra-site insights and will finish by emphasizing some regional aspects.

The first case study consists in the site of Gird-i Qulq Hurd (HDS.21 or SSP.19), located on the northeastern part of the Shahrizor Plain, 12 km west of the Iranian border. It is an approximately 10 m high mound, providing an excellent control point over the area. The top of the site has a gentle slope from south to north. Military features have been spotted on top of

the site by GeoEye satellite imagery from 2013²⁴ and then surveyed directly on site. These features are composed of a surrounding trench (Figure 7.1), marked with firing positions to the west, south and east (Figure 7.2), a secondary trench to the north (Figure 7.3), and a large depression between the two trenches that is of the exact same size as a medium unit barracks of 6.7 m by 6.8 m (Figure 7.4). In this case, the intervisibility analysis helps to understand the points of interest visible from the installation.

The various analyses have revealed that a military occupation oriented towards the south offered a larger observation angle towards the plain (Figure 8.a). There is, however, no evidence of a military barracks in the southern perimeter of the site.

23. Ground-to-ground also includes shots from artillery positions such as stationed tanks. Yet, unless effort is made to trace back to the ammunition used it is very difficult to distinguish it from air-to-ground strikes. In our case differentiation between the two was not possible based on remotely sensed data.

24. BingImagery plugin in ArcGIS.

FIG. 7: Satellite view of Grdy Qulk Hurd (HDS.21 or SSP.19) showing the military features present on site 1. Surrounding trench 2. Firing positions 3. Secondary trench 4. Barrack's probable location, BingImagery 2013.

Besides, a visible cut, the size of a medium unit barracks, indicates a military settlement in the northern part of the site, where the observation angle is clearly narrower than in the southern part. The military settlement is looking specifically into the valley and the Iranian border, neglecting the plain due to the inclination of the top (Figure 8.b). This analysis sheds light on the control points targeted by the military. Such observations confirm that the military occupation is rooted in the context of the Iran-Iraq War from 1980 to 1988. Furthermore, an occupation by the Iraqi forces is most likely at Gird-i Qulk Hurd (HDS.21 or SSP.19) since the mound protects the plain from a possible intrusion coming from the valley which connects it to Iran.

The second case study, on Bngird Muani (HDS.44 or SSP.12), underlines the potential of 3D modelling for a better understanding of the military occupation of archaeological sites. The 3D modelling of the site, using photogrammetry, has been made possible thanks to the drone flight and photography taken and processed by Rémi Méreuzé (Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne, UMR 8096, ArchAm) within the framework of ICONEM.

FIG. 8: Inter-visibility analysis for Grdy Qulk Hurd (HDS.21 or SSP.19) based on SRTM imagery, realized under ArcGIS software.

The main objective of such approach is to highlight the levelling and the excavation of trenches on top of the site. Therefore, I have used the processed Digital Elevation Model (DEM), whose histogram of values is reduced to the values of the top, thus providing a good visibility of the trenches (Figure 9). This enabled to extract north to south and east to west sections from the DEM and to reveal the presence of a second trench. This double trench from west to north was hardly visible on satellite imagery (CORONA, DigitalGlobe Imagery, etc.) and its presence attests to a protection system oriented towards the northwest valley, visible from the site as shown on the intervisibility analysis (Figure 10).

FIG. 9: DEM extracted from the 3D model of Bngrd Muani (HDS.44 or SSP.12), R. Méreuze.

This combined analysis shows that the occupation of the site served several purposes of control. As a matter of facts, the site offers a good visibility on the plain to the south and also on two strategic locations to the north (the northwest valley and the northeast pass). This was confirmed by information gathered from interviews with Gird-i Muani villagers. According to the local population, the site was indeed continuously occupied from the early 1980s until the end of the Iran-Iraq War. As far as they could remember, the site had a softly rounded profile. It was firstly used as a police station to control the area during the 1980s, and was later on slightly flattened on the top in order to install a military position by the end of the conflict to control the movements through the mountains coming from and going to Iran. Such information matches exactly the observations made on the DEM, the photogrammetry and the intervisibility analysis. The results shed light on the strategic interest of the army for the northwestern valley and the northeastern

pass through the mountains.

The third case study, located in Afghanistan, aims at underlining the strategic differences between Balkh and the Shahrizor Plain. Adina Masjid (BDS.131) is located slightly off to the west from the centre of the Balkh Oasis. Contrary to the Iraqi sites, it does not hold any strategic value within the landscape (not protecting any access point, far from major cities, etc.).

The installation consists of multiple sections of trenches surrounding the tell and creating a rudimentary maze. The lower outside trench (Figure 11.1) is open to the east, while the inside one (Figure 11.2) displays a double opening to the east and west and the inside space is equipped with smaller sections of trench to the east creating a honeycomb layout (Figure 11.3). It should nevertheless be noted that there was no land preparation for this installation, with namely no levelling of the top of the site. No firing position could either be identified.

Most of the military occupied sites of the Oasis display the same kind of rudimentary defence, with earthen barracks in some cases. In this area, the Taliban's objectives was to create a tight mesh of military of occupation in order to control the territory rather than to defend a particular position. The closest to Balkh and Mazar-i Charif the tightest is the mesh and loosening towards the extremity of the Oasis as there is no access point and the natural protection of the dunes to the north.

FIG. 10: Inter-visibility analysis for Bngrd Muani (HDS. 44 or SSP.12), based on SRTM imagery, realized under ArcGIS software.

In the studied areas, Kurdish and Afghan alike, the documentation is very scarce regarding the actions of both warring parties and the precise history of the fighting. It is even scantier on the actions of small armed groups that may have operated in the background of the conflicts. Both areas appear not to belong

to the wider narrative told in Western academic publications²⁵.

Even in some Kurdish²⁶ and Afghan publications²⁷, Halabja and Mazar-i Charif are mentioned only very briefly. That is so in spite of their respective importance in the Anfal campaign of 1988 for Halabja and the fights that have been shaking Mazar-i Charif since the 1990s.

Archaeological remains and interviews with locals are, in the current state of knowledge, the best sources of evidence to reconstruct the untold story of conflicts. In Iraq, the spatial reading of the occupied sites at a regional scale shows a predominance of occupied sites on the east border, looking towards Iran. In the isolated area of HDS (Figure 12), controlling the access points may have been the priority of the military strategy with a

lesser interest in the movements in the plain. Military occupied sites are located around the Darband-i Khan lake and mainly looking out to the southeastern and the eastern mountains.

The Afghan area displays a very different pattern (Figure 13), with a dense occupation in a more open landscape. Indeed, this flat open area is bounded by natural features, with the dunes to the north and the mountain ridge and the pass to the south. Even if visibility over the northern and southern borders is aimed at, inside control along the many canals of the Oasis also seems to be a priority, which would explain the high density of occupied sites on the western part of the Oasis. Military bases are homogeneously distributed, and the variability of their densities is also related to the density of archaeological tells.

FIG. 11: Satellite view of Adina Masjid (BDS.131) showing the military features present on site 1. Lower trench 2. Inside trench 3. Sections of trenches for inside separation DigitalGlobe Imagery, GeoEye 2016.

25. CHUBIN & TRIPP 1988; MALEY 2009; ASHTON & GIBSON 2013.

26. BARZANI 2009.

27. The case of Afghanistan is even more specific as national authors are represented mainly in local newspapers and therefore concentrating on targeted events.

FIG. 12: Regional inter-visibility analysis for HDS based on SRTM imagery, realized under ArcGIS software.

FIG. 13: Regional inter-visibility analysis for BDS based on SRTM imagery, realized under ArcGIS software.

CONCLUSION

Several points can be raised as a general conclusion for this study. Military damages are significantly disturbing the stratigraphy of archaeological sites even though they are mostly located on the upper areas of the tells. Data gathered for developing new archaeological strategies on these damaged sites can also be used for documenting modern conflicts in order to get some historical insight. This archaeological perspective is especially relevant in remote areas located far from the battlefield and set aside by historians and political science academics alike. In fact, studying the inlands of the conflict zones would enable us to gain a new and more definite knowledge on the everyday life of the soldiers. This kind of study, combined with a more traditional approach, would then provide a more precise view of the conflicts and lead to shaping a history of military occupation. It could also provide a better understanding and perception of border-areas during conflicts. In the case studies I presented, I have noticed the variability of military strategies and occupation on the one hand. On the other, I have underlined the impacts recurrence into the stratigraphy. Documenting war remains with as much efforts and thoroughness as is devoted to

documenting ancient remains would certainly be a valuable asset to gain more insight into the topic. In those regions where information about the history of certain conflicts can be scarce, such information could provide valuable extra data recorded as much as a part of history that as a disturbance to the deeper levels.

That remote sensing and satellite imagery analysis²⁸ as it is now widely developed for monitoring damages²⁹ can be used for both documenting armed conflict and preparing scientific activities such as excavations is self-evident. Both analysis might also be used as a base to excavate the latest layers of occupation dated to the modern conflict period, and to understand the disturbances to ancient stratigraphic levels. Not to mention that it can also be possible to take advantage of military ground modifications and cuts to reach deeper archaeological layers as part of an inventive methodology. Finally, this article argues for the necessity to excavate military occupations following archaeological methodology in order to fill the gaps in not so well-known armed conflicts, from the daily life of the military to understanding the various battle strategies.

28. HANSON & EMBERLING 2008; CUNLIFFE 2013.

29. To cite only two : ASOR CHI and EAMENA projects for instance.

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